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Ecological Proxies to the Bioremediation of Crude Oil Polluted Mangrove Soil Obtained from Okerenkoko, Delta State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The impact of pollutants on the mangrove ecosystem has caused several ecological challenges to man and his quest to survive. The activities of illegal oil exploitation and the regulatory agencies have impeded the success of reducing the presence of pollutants in the ecosystem. The mangrove soil samples were obtained from the creeks of Okerenkoko, Delta State, Nigeria and transported to the laboratory. Physicochemical components were determined using analytical grade reagents and procedures. Agro waste was obtained from the markets, slaughterhouses and mills and processed into portions for the bioremediation study. The earthen pots were prepared using 5kg of the polluted soil obtained from the study area using 10% oil palm empty fruit bunch ash, 20% Rumen waste and 30% wood shavings. The study identified a 90% reduction in total petroleum hydrocarbons using the composite in the experiment with composite mixtures of the feedstock. The total heterotrophic bacterial count increased from 6.8 Log₁₀ CFU/g to 8.8 Log₁₀ CFU/g while the soil pH increased from 6.2 to 6.7. The predominant flora consisted of *Bacillus* sp., *Aeromonas* sp., and *Pseudomonas* sp. After the 8th week of the study, *Pseudomonas* sp. and *Staphylococcus* sp. were identified as playing a crucial role in achieving the reduction of the pollutant. Molecular investigations revealed that the isolates obtained were *Bacillus axarquiensis* and *Pseudomonas guguanensis*, with 100% similarity with the already deposited organisms in the GENBANK. This study has shed light on the potential of using readily available biomass and feedstock in the resolution of our environmental challenges

Keywords: Ecological proxies, Pollutants, Mangrove ecosystems, Oil palm empty fruit bunch ash, feedstock, Biomass

1. INTRODUCTION

Mangrove ecosystems are unique and essential coastal ecosystems, endowed with their rich fauna and flora. They exhibit resilient adaptation to salinity, nutrient depletion and fluxes in oxygen levels [1]. Mangroves are believed to equal the productivity of the tropical rainforest; since they account for about 1.0% of the earth's cover, they are widely assumed to be the most productive ecosystems due to the number of biological activities that occur. The nature of mangrove ecosystems is critical to their ability to host evergreen vegetation and wildlife; this is because mangroves may provide a milieu of uses, such as nesting and serving as a carbon sink. The vegetation is characterised by species diversity, tidal flow, and organic matter from plant litter. Physiologically, morphologically and ecologically, they are structurally adapted to oligotrophic environments. The mangrove soil or swamp is part of the ecosystem where nutrients needed for the survival of the plants are sequestered for its macrohabitat and microhabitat. In most mangrove ecosystems, the physicochemical components differ from one location to another. The soil in most mangrove components is built from estuarine habitat deposits, while the intertidal forces affect the concentration of nutrients in the ecosystem. These ecosystems are believed to play a crucial role in the balance and reabsorption of greenhouse gases to ameliorate the challenges of climate change. Despite the volume of information on the mangroves, there is significantly limited information on their habitat, biodiversity and geochemistry [2]. The impact of anthropogenic activities on the quality of biological activities in most mangrove ecosystems.

The activity of illegal crude oil exploration in Nigeria is becoming disturbing, and like the activities of the surveillance industry, it has eased the burden of pollution in the region. The rate of pollution of critical ecosystems by the destruction of facilities involved in oil exploitation has increased in recent times. The contents of crude oil have been associated with oncogenes, which can impede several biological activities [3-5]. This is because they prevent the permeation of nutrients and availability to microbiota and flora. The worst effects of pollutants like crude oil are their resistance and recalcitrance in the environment, causing chronic damage to the flow of nutrients. In recent times, the rate of pollution due to the sabotage of facilities by thieves has increased geometrically, polluting sensitive ecosystems like the mangroves. Leaks, facility failures, accidents, and sabotage by host communities have taken centre stage in public discussion on the cause and treatment of the impacted environment [6]. Corrective measures have involved several biological, chemical and physical approaches. Bioremediation is the application of biological systems and their products in the conversion of very toxic materials to less harmful ones.

The techniques in bioremediation can be interpreted as the use of the biodegradability of materials [7]. The technology is considered relatively cheap and accessible, with applications in several sectors. This technology can be divided based on the site of the application, the changes to the site and the nature of the site. The changes in the physico-chemistry of the soil as a defining factor to the success of the remediation of several sites [8].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study Area

Map of Okerenkoko showing points of sample collection points (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Map of Okerenkoko showing points of sample collection points.

2. 2. Experimental Design for Bioremediation

Table 1. Experimental Design for Bioremediation.

Experimental setup	Test experiment
A	5 kg of polluted soil + 10% OPEMFB-ASH
B	5 kg of polluted soil + 10% OPEMFB-ASH + 20% RW
C	5 kg of polluted soil + 10% OPEMFB-ASH + 20% RW+ 30% WS
D	5 kg PS alone (Baseline)

2. 3. Sample collection

A simple handheld auger was used to sample the mangrove soil, and a pristine auger was applied to the soil's 0-30 cm depth. The soil sample was packaged and transported to the

biological sciences laboratory at Edwin Clark University, Kiagbodo, where Dr Effiong and his team analysed the samples [4, 9, 10].

2. 4. Determination of physicochemical components of the mangrove soil

The physicochemical composition of the soil was determined using the modified method of Agbaji et al. [4], principally adopting grade reagent and procedures of the Tarab *et al.*, [11] parameters, such as pH, Temperature, and conductivity, were measured using a highly sensitive meter with already calibrated probes. The chemical components evaluated after the samples were digested for analysis, such as nitrate. The presence of heavy metals and metals was determined by adopting the modified method of Asionye *et al.*, [12] using the Atomic Absorption Spectra and Gas Chromatography- Flame ionising detectors [1]

2. 5. Proximate composition of agro waste

Determination of the elemental or mineral composition of the feedstock for the study is presented below. The oil palm empty fruit bunch ash was sought and collected from a mill in Elibrada, Emohua, L.G.A, Rivers State, Nigeria. The rumen content of the cattle was obtained from the slaughterhouse at the Ubogo market of Delta State. The wood shavings were obtained from the dump section of the wood market by express junction, Delta State. The agro waste was processed by pulverising it at a local blending section at Ubogo market in Otor-Udu, LGA of Delta State. They were bagged and transported in sealed bags to the biological sciences laboratory at Edwin Clark University.

2. 6. Monitoring of Bioremediation Proxies

The monitoring of the total heterotrophic bacterial count was done using the modified method of Udume *et al.*, [13]. The monitoring of the hydrocarbon-utilising bacterial count followed the modified method of Orji et al., [14], which employed the vapour-phase transfer method using mineral salt agar (Oxoid). The determination of the fungal population in the experimental setup employed the use of spread plate technique on potatoes dextrose agar, the media was fortified with 1% lactic acid while population of the hydrocarbon utilizing fungi was determined using [15, 16] by inhibiting the growth of bacterial flora by adding 100 µg/ml to an already lukewarm media

2. 7. Biochemical identification of bacterial isolates

Identification of the bacterial isolates followed the modified method of Cheesebrough [17]. The process involved using 18-hour-old pure cultures of the isolates. The isolates were later sub-cultured on slants for further studies.

2. 8. Molecular identification of bacterial isolates

The extraction of the genomic DNA followed the boiling approach as previously reported by Agbaji et al. [4]. The kits obtained from Inqaba-South Africa are called the Zymo Fungal/Bacteria DNA extraction kit. The amplification was carried out using the 16S rRNA universal primers. The Solis Biodyne was used for the reaction, while the 1.5% agarose gel was used for the gel electrophoresis.

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Physicochemical composition of soil samples obtained from the study area

Table 2 shows the physicochemical composition of the crude oil-polluted mangrove soil obtained from the Kiagbodo, Delta State, Nigeria. The pH of the mangrove soil and pristine soil were 6.40 and 7.3, respectively. The temperature of the soil samples obtained from pristine mangrove soil was 27.6 °C, while the impacted mangrove soil had 29.10 °C. The moisture content of the crude oil-polluted mangrove soil was 40.80% while the pristine soil had 64.5%; the conductivity of the crude oil-polluted mangrove soil was 168.40 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$ while the pristine soil had a conductivity of 100.55 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$. The nitrate content of the polluted mangrove soil was 0.13 mg/kg, while the pristine soil had 0.36 mg/kg; the iron content for the crude-oil-polluted mangrove soil was 6.30 mg/kg, while the pristine soil had 2.78 mg/kg. The total petroleum hydrocarbon of the polluted mangrove soil samples was 9661.80 mg/kg, while the pristine soil had 20.90 mg/kg. The polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in the crude oil-polluted mangrove soil were 176.40 mg/kg, while the pristine soil had 1.12 mg/kg. The total heterotrophic bacterial count of the crude oil-impacted mangrove soil was 4.03 Log_{10} CFU/g, while the pristine soil had 7.10 Log_{10} CFU/g. The hydrocarbon utilising bacterial count observed was 3.10 Log_{10} CFU/g and 2.80 Log_{10} CFU/g for the polluted and pristine soil samples, respectively.

Table 2. Physicochemical composition of the crude oil-polluted mangrove soil obtained from the Gbaramatu Kingdom, Delta State, Nigeria

Parameters	Mangrove soil	Pristine soil
pH	6.40	7.3
Temperature (°C)	29.10	27.6
Moisture content (%)	40.80	64.5
Conductivity ($\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$)	168.40	100.55
Nitrate (mg/Kg)	0.13	0.36
Iron (mg/kg)	6.30	2.78
Cadmium (mg/kg)	0.17	0.015
Lead (mg/kg)	9.78	0.075
Chromium (mg/kg)	11.90	<0.001
Copper (mg/kg)	43.40	12.30
Zinc (mg/kg)	20.95	6.55
TOC (%)	34.20	19.20
Phosphate (mg/Kg)	1.02	1.14
TPH	9,661.80	20.90

PAH	176.40	1.12
THC	28,946.00	498.50
PAH	179.40	<0.001
THB (Log ₁₀ CFU/g)	4.03	7.10
HUB (Log ₁₀ CFU/g)	3.10	2.80
TFC (Log ₁₀ CFU/g)	2.55	2.10
HUF (Log ₁₀ CFU/g)	2.10	2.0

TPH - Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon; PAH - Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon, THC- Total Hydrocarbon Content - Key: CFU/g: colony forming unit/gram. Total Heterotrophic Bacteria; Hydrocarbon Utilizing Bacteria; Total Fungi count; HUF - Hydrocarbon Utilizing Fungi

3. 2. Proximate composition of the feedstock for bioremediation of polluted mangrove soil

The result presented in Table 3 shows the proximate composition of the biomass utilised for the study. The concentration of nitrate in the rumen waste was 9.67 mg/kg, while phosphate in the Oil palm empty fruit bunch was 79.33 mg/kg the wood shavings had a carbon concentration of 115.1 mg/kg.

Table 3. Proximate composition of biomass.

Biomass	Carbon	Nitrate	Phosphates
Rumen Waste	115.1 mg/kg	9.67 mg/kg	2.49 mg/kg
Wood Shavings	1167.5 mg/kg	0.12 mg/kg	1.12 mg/kg
Oil Palm Empty fruit Bunch	23.6 mg/kg	0.04 mg/kg	79.33 mg/kg

3. 3. Bioremediation proxies

The bioremediation proxies that defined the treatment of the polluted mangrove soil were presented in Tables 4 & 5. The total petroleum hydrocarbon treatment using OPEFB -ash was observed to reduce from 26342.02 mg/kg on the first day of the treatment to 22860.08 mg/kg on the 8th week of the study; similarly, the concentration of the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon was observed to drop from an initial concentration of 18670.04 mg/kg to 16670.68 mg/kg on the 8th week of the study. Conversely, the treatment reduced 5.8 Log₁₀CFU/g to 6.56 Log₁₀CFU/g on the 8th week of the study, while the total hydrocarbon-utilising bacterial count 4.33 Log₁₀CFU/g to 5.63 Log₁₀CFU/g. The pH of the experimental set-up was observed to decrease from 6.20 to 6.0, with fluctuations between the first and second weeks of the study.

The result presented in Table 5 shows the bioremediation of the mangrove soil polluted with crude oil being treated with OPEFB and cow rumen. The result showed a remarkable reduction in total petroleum hydrocarbons as it dropped from 22552.72 mg/kg to 2048.72 mg/kg

after the 8th week of treatment, while the concentration of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons dropped from an initial concentration of 15967.62 to 999.98mg/kg on the 8th week of treatment. The biological proxies of the bioremediation showed a sharp increase in the population of the total heterotrophic bacterial count from 5.63 Log₁₀CFU/g to 7.60 Log₁₀CFU/g after the 8-week duration; total hydrocarbon-utilising bacterial count increased from an initial concentration of 5.5 Log₁₀CFU/g to 7.63 Log₁₀CFU/g on the 8th week of the study. The pH of the experimental setup was observed to reduce from 6.2 to 6.13 on the 6th week of the study, although the 8th week observed that the pH of the study remained 6.0.

Table 4. Bioremediation proxies for mangrove soil polluted with crude oil and OPEFB -ash.

Duration	TPH	PAH	THBC	THUB	[THB/HUB]	pH
0	26342.02	18670.04	5.80	4.33	1.34	6.20
1	26281.48	18453.78	5.82	4.38	1.33	6.34
2	26007.18	18302.21	6.84	5.69	1.20	6.31
4	25742.11	18198.05	6.83	5.75	1.41	6.10
6	23808.76	16789.22	6.79	5.68	1.19	6.00
8	22860.08	16670.68	6.56	5.63	1.16	6.00

Table 5. Bioremediation proxies for mangrove soil polluted with crude oil, OPEFB -ash+ Cow dung.

Duration	TPH	PAH	THBC	THUB	[THB/HUB]	pH
0	22552.72	15967.62	5.63	5.50	1.03	6.20
1	14125.65	10040.63	6.70	5.86	1.14	6.10
2	7844.90	6058.28	6.98	7.83	0.92	6.11
4	5646.52	4083.49	8.21	7.92	1.01	6.10
6	3555.93	2400.11	7.97	7.90	1.01	6.13
8	2048.72	999.98	7.60	7.63	1.00	6.00

Bioremediation of the mangrove soil using a composite containing OPEFB-ash, cow rumen and wood shavings was presented in Table 6. The bioremediation of crude oil-polluted mangrove soil using OPEFB-ash, cow rumen and wood shavings was defined by the drop in the concentration of the TPH reduced from 21701.7 mg/kg to 265.10 mg/kg; the concentration of PAHs decreased from 15308.37 to 153.22 mg/kg after the 8-week study. The total heterotrophic bacterial count increased from 6.80 Log₁₀ CFU/g to 7.8 Log₁₀ CFU/g after an

8-week duration. The concentration of the hydrocarbon-utilising bacterial population increased from 4.40 Log₁₀ CFU/g to 8.63 Log₁₀ CFU/g after the 8-week study. The pH was observed to increase from 6.2 to 6.7 between the first day of setup and the final day of study.

Table 6. Bioremediation proxies for mangrove soil polluted with crude oil, OPEFB -ash, cow rumen and wood shavings.

Duration	TPH	PAH	THBC	THUB	[THB/HUB]	pH
0	21701.71	15308.37	6.80	4.40	0.65	6.2
1	9566.25	7254.36	6.56	5.30	0.81	6.3
2	5875.32	4156.71	7.90	7.68	0.97	6.5
4	2515.18	2077.20	8.91	8.92	1.00	6.6
6	1088.79	1080.86	8.86	8.74	1.11	6.6
8	265.10	153.23	8.80	8.63	1.11	6.7

3. 4. Distribution of Microbial flora during the bioremediation of crude oil-polluted mangrove soil obtained from Okerenkoko, Delta State, Nigeria

The results presented in Table 7 show the distribution of bacterial flora during the bioremediation of the polluted mangrove soil samples. The experimental design using OPEFB-ash had *Pseudomonas* sp. and *Bacillus* sp., while in the 8th week, the most predominant organisms were still the same organisms. In the 6th week, *Micrococcus* sp., *Bacillus* sp., and *Pseudomonas* sp. were the most predominant flora, while in week 2, *Bacillus* sp. was the predominant. The treatment using a composite of agro waste (OPEFB-ash+rw+ws) was observed to have *Bacillus* sp., *Aeromonas* sp., and *Pseudomonas* sp. as the most frequent bacterial isolates in the initial set of bioremediation studies. After 8 weeks, the predominant bacterial isolates were *Bacillus* sp. and *Pseudomonas* sp.

Table 8 shows the distribution of fungal flora observed in the experimental setup designed using the oil-palm empty fruit bunch was observed to have a high concentration of *Aspergillus* sp, *Rhodotorula* sp. and *Candida* sp. while on the 8th week was observed to have *Phoma* sp., *Mucor* sp., and *Aspergillus* sp. were recorded on the 8th week of the study while the composite mixture of the agro waste was observed to have the following *Cladosporium* sp., *Aspergillus* sp. and *Penicillium* sp. on the initial day of the study while after the 8th week *Penicillium* sp., *Rhizopus* sp. and *Cladosporium* sp. were reported.

3. 5. Molecular Identification of the bacterial isolates obtained during the study.

The result is presented in Figure 2. Shows the molecular weight of the extracted DNA of the bacterial isolates on a 1% agarose gel. The resolved amplicons presented below show the bands of 6.5kbp on 16S primer sets. The Isolates obtained from the study after the performance of phylogenetic studies were identified the isolates a with the already deposited organisms in the GENBANK.

Table 7. Bacterial isolates obtained during the bioremediation of crude oil-polluted Mangrove soil obtained from Gbaramatu Kingdom.

Week	PS+ OPEFB-ash	PS+ OPEFB-ash+RW	PS+ OPEFB-ash+RW+WS
0	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp.	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. <i>Proteus</i> sp.	<i>Bacillus</i> sp. <i>Aeromonas</i> sp. <i>Pseudomonas</i>
1	<i>Bacillus</i> sp. <i>Micrococcus</i> sp.	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. <i>Staphylococcus</i> sp.	<i>Aeromonas</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp.
2	<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	<i>Micrococcus</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp.	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. <i>Aeromonas</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp.
4	<i>Micrococcus</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp. <i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.	<i>Micrococcus</i> sp. <i>Aerobacter</i> sp.	<i>Aeromonas</i> sp. <i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. <i>Micrococcus</i> sp.
6	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp. <i>Thiobacillus</i> sp.	<i>Micrococcus</i> sp. <i>Klebsiella</i> sp. <i>Streptococcus</i> sp.	<i>Aeromonas</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp.
8	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. <i>Bacillus</i> sp.	<i>Chromobacter</i> sp. <i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. <i>Proteus</i> sp.	<i>Bacillus</i> sp. <i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. <i>Staphylococcus</i> sp.

Table 8. Fungal isolates obtained during the bioremediation of crude oil-polluted Mangrove soil obtained from Gbaramatu Kingdom, Delta State, Nigeria.

Duration	PS+ OPEFB-ash	PS+ OPEFB-ash+RW	PS+ OPEFB-ash+RW+WS
0	<i>Rhodotorula</i> sp. <i>Aspergillus</i> sp. <i>Candida</i> sp.	<i>Mucor</i> sp. <i>Fusarium</i> sp. <i>Candida</i> sp. <i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	<i>Cladosporium</i> sp. <i>Aspergillus</i> sp. <i>Penicillium</i> sp.
8	<i>Phoma</i> sp <i>Mucor</i> sp. <i>Aspergillus</i> sp. <i>Candida</i> sp.	<i>Candida</i> sp <i>Aspergillus</i> sp. <i>Mucor</i> sp.	<i>Penicillium</i> sp. <i>Rhizopus</i> sp. <i>Cladosporium</i> sp. <i>Candida</i> sp.

3. 6. Molecular profiling of 16SrRNA bacterial isolates obtained during the remediation

Figure 2. Agarose gel electrophoresis for the 16S band (1500bp) of the isolates. Lane C represents the control while lane M represents 1kb quick-load molecular ladder.

Table 9. RNA identification of bacterial isolates.

S/No	Isolate code	BlastN identity	Percentage similarity (%)	Accession number
1	0A1	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	92	KX664101
2	8E1	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	73	KT250766.1
3	4B1	<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>	99	KC525245.1
4	2C1	<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>	99	CP007437.1

Figure 3. Phylogenetic Tree Construct

4. DISCUSSION

Pollution has remained a challenge in the Niger Delta, in recent times; the spate of events leading to the unwarranted destruction of crude oil facilities in the region to sabotage by illegal crude exploitation has increased geometrically. This present study recorded a baseline concentration of pH 6.40 for the polluted mangrove soil, while the pristine sample had 7.3. This study corroborates the previous report of Dewiyanti *et al.* [18], whose study reported 6.9 for the baseline studies, although several samples had a pH of 7.4. They asserted that the subsurface concentration values were due to reabsorption and the litter that may decompose over time, causing a change in the soil's pH. According to Agbaji *et al.* [4], the pH of a soil sample can give insight into the stability of nutrients and their bioavailability for metabolic activities.

The rate of reduction of the total petroleum hydrocarbon treatment using OPEFB -ash was observed to reduce from 26342.02 mg/kg on the first day of the treatment to 22860.08 mg/kg on the 8th week of the study; similarly, the concentration of the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon was observed to drop from an initial concentration of 18670.04 mg/kg to 16670.68

mg/kg on the 8th week of the study. Conversely, the treatment reduced to 5.8 Log₁₀CFU/g to 6.56 Log₁₀CFU/g on the 8th week of the study, while the total hydrocarbon-utilising bacterial count 4.33 Log₁₀CFU/g to 5.63 Log₁₀CFU/g. The pH of the experimental set-up was observed to decrease from 6.20 to 6.0, with fluctuations between the first and second weeks of the study.

This correlates with the report of Agbaji *et al.* [4], whose report was conducted using a bioremediation cocktail that reported an increase in the 3.77 Log₁₀CFU/g to 7.60 Log₁₀CFU/g. While Orhororo *et al.* [20] reported an increase in the microbial population, Form reported an increase from 4.34 Log₁₀CFU/g to 6.50 Log₁₀CFU/g. Similarly, Onifade *et al.* [19] had previously posited that an increase in the population of microbes suggested an increase in the stability of microbial indices. The work of Ijah and Antai (2003) reported that microbes have an amazing utilise crude oil as a source of energy *Bacillus*, *Lactobacter*, *Arthrobacter*, *Pseudomonas*, *Micrococcus*, *Zoopage* and *Articulosporium*. This strongly corroborates the findings in our study we identified the presence of *Aeromonas sp.*, *Pseudomonas sp.*, *Bacillus sp.*, *Proteus sp.*, *Micrococcus sp.*, *Aerobacter* and *Chromobacter sp.*, and *Thiobacillus sp.*

These also agreed with the report of Onifade *et al.* [19], whose study documented the following *Lactobacillus*, *Arthrobacter*, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas* and *Micrococcus sp.* Orhororo *et al.* [20] previously identified *Bacillus sp.* and *Pseudomonas sp.* from crude oil-polluted soil. In a related study, Babalola *et al.* [21] reported that *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were isolated from a slurry-phase bioremediation.

In a similar vein, the fungal flora observed during bioremediation studies were *Rhodotorula sp.*, *Aspergillus sp.* and *Candida sp.* were observed in the setup containing the Oil palm empty fruit bunch ash on the first week of the study, while after the 8th week of the study, *Phom asp* and *Mucor sp* were observed during the study. The molecular evaluation of the bacterial isolates observed in the bioremediation studies was as *Bacillus axarquiensis* with a similarity of 100% and was identified as *Pseudomonas guguanensis* with 100% similarity.

These findings corroborate the report of Ezekoye *et al.* [22], whose molecular studies identified the presence of Firmicutes, which is a classification holding *Bacillus sp.*, while Gammaproteobacteria were identified, which is the classification holding *Pseudomonas aeruginous*. Previous studies have reported that the members of this classification had a remarkable mechanism for breaking down crude oil.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The level of pollution caused by the crude oil theft and the regulatory agencies through their surveillance program has left a bitter taste in the mouths of the indigent populace and stressed the already depleted natural resources. The concentration of pollutants like the total petroleum hydrocarbons and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in the mangrove was higher than a tier 1 level of pollution. The PAH and TPH at the point of sampling from the reconnaissance survey were 9661.80 mg/kg and 176.4 mg/kg, which was largely after the destruction of the barge carrying illegal crude through the ESCRAVOS platform. The study further identified the niche of biomass that has been poorly or underreported in studies on the remediation of crude oil spills. The reduction in the concentration of TPH by over 80% was indicative of the addition of information to the wealth of existing knowledge. The researchers are positing possible legislation for the recovery of stolen crude instead of discharge and destruction, as they may cause chronic challenges to non-target ecosystems like the mangroves.

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